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10 **The influence of physical fitness attributes on external demands**
11 **during simulated basketball matches in youth players according to**
12 **age category**

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14 **Running head:** Fitness and match demands in youth basketball.

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34 **Abstract**

35 This study aimed to: 1) compare physical fitness attributes and the external demands
36 encountered during simulated matches in youth basketball players between age categories
37 (under 14 years [U14], under 16 years [U16], and under 18 years [U18]), and 2) examine the
38 relationships between physical fitness attributes and external demands during simulated
39 matches in each age category. Thirty young basketball players categorized according to age
40 (U14, n = 10; U16, n = 10; and U18, n = 10) completed a fitness test battery consisting of linear
41 sprint, change-of-direction speed, repeated-change-of-direction speed, and jump assessments,
42 and simulated matches monitored using local positioning system technology one week later.
43 One-way analyses of variance (ANOVA) with Bonferroni post hoc tests, as well as Cohen's
44 effect sizes were used to compare physical fitness attributes and external match demands
45 between age categories. Pearson's correlations and linear regression analyses were performed
46 to quantify the relationships and shared variance between physical fitness attributes and
47 external match demands in each age category. U14 players possessed lower ($p < 0.05$, *large-*
48 *very large* effects) physical fitness across all tests and performed less ($p < 0.05$, *large-very large*
49 effects) high-speed running ($18.1\text{-}24.0 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) during simulated matches than U16 and U18
50 players. Physical fitness attributes were significantly associated with external variables during
51 simulated matches in each category, particularly in U14 players. These findings suggest
52 coaches should implement training strategies targeting specific fitness attributes according to
53 age in youth basketball players.

54 **Key words:** speed; power; anaerobic; performance; workload; game; team sports.

55 **1. Introduction**

56 Basketball is a multi-dimensional team sport in which successful performance is predicated on
57 developing optimal physical condition, tactical ability, technical skill, and psychological
58 attributes [1]. A major objective for basketball high-performance and coaching staff is to
59 understand the predominant physical fitness attributes underpinning optimal physical
60 condition, which in turn likely positively influences the activity volumes and intensities able
61 to be attained by players during matches [2]. Through identifying the influence of physical
62 fitness attributes on the activities performed (i.e. external demands) during matches, basketball
63 coaches may be able to better develop appropriate individualized training stimuli to optimize
64 the physical preparedness of players for competition [3].

65 While identifying key physical fitness attributes associated with match activity may prove
66 useful, player fitness and match activity vary with age, particularly in youth basketball players
67 since physical condition in children and adolescents is dependent on several factors mediated
68 by growth and maturation [4,5]. Comprehensive evidence has not been generated regarding the
69 extent which physical fitness varies with age in youth basketball players. In this regard,
70 research has shown repeated-sprint ability and aerobic fitness to progressively increase with
71 age in state-level, Italian, youth male basketball players aged 9-15 years [5], and jumping
72 capacity, sprint speed, and aerobic fitness to be greater at 16 years of age compared to 14 years
73 of age in state- and national-level, Australian youth basketball players [4]. In contrast, other
74 research has shown similar jumping capacity, sprint speed, change-of-direction (COD) speed,
75 and repeated-sprint ability in elite Spanish, female players under 16 years of age (U16) and
76 under 18 years of age (U18) [6]. Consequently, the existing research indicates youth basketball
77 players may increase physical fitness attributes up to 16 years of age with plateaus in fitness
78 thereafter; however, further examination is needed on this topic given the limited evidence
79 available. Given basketball high-performance and coaching staff seek to optimally develop

80 physical fitness attributes in basketball players that enable them to best cope with the demands
81 encountered as well as outperform their opponents from a physical standpoint during matches,
82 an understanding of differences in the activities performed during matches across age
83 categories in youth basketball players seems essential. Despite this logic, no research has
84 compared the external demands experienced during matches between different age categories
85 in youth basketball players, making it difficult to ascertain whether physical fitness attributes
86 in players align with the age-specific competitive demands faced.

87 Sufficient physical fitness in basketball players across age categories and playing levels is
88 essential to cope with the specific external demands encountered during matches [7].
89 Therefore, important fitness attributes in basketball should be assessed using tests that replicate
90 specific actions and movement sequences stressed during match-play. In this regard, limited
91 research has quantified the association between neuromuscular, anaerobic, or aerobic fitness
92 tests with external demands during basketball matches in youth players. Only one study has
93 examined associations between performance during strength, jump, sprint, COD, and aerobic
94 fitness tests and the external demands encountered during matches in young, national-level,
95 Tunisian, male basketball players (18.2 ± 0.5 years of age) [8]. Specifically, Ben Abdelkrim et
96 al. [8] reported COD performance time ($r = -0.68$) and aerobic capacity ($r = 0.64$) to be
97 significantly associated with high-intensity shuffling and running distances covered during
98 matches, respectively. Despite this evidence, data were not provided comprehensively in a wide
99 sample of youth players spanning various age groups, which remains uninvestigated.

100 Consequently, the aims of this study were to: 1) compare physical fitness attributes and the
101 external demands encountered during simulated matches in youth basketball players between
102 age categories (under 14 years of age [U14], U16, and U18); and 2) examine the relationships
103 between physical fitness attributes and external demands during simulated matches in each age
104 category.

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2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study design

A cross-sectional, observational study design was adopted. Initially, players had anthropometric measurements taken and completed a fitness test battery across two separate days. On the first testing day, anthropometric data and jumping performance were measured in laboratory conditions (17–22°C, 60–70% relative humidity). Prior to the jumping test, all players performed a standardized warm-up consisting of cycling at a moderate intensity for 5 min, followed by 5 min of jumps performed at progressively increasing intensities, and 5 min of dynamic stretching exercises. On the second day, players performed various fitness tests in the same order, including 20-m linear sprint, COD, and repeated change-of-direction (RCOD) tests on an indoor basketball court (15–18°C, 60–70% relative humidity), with 5 min of passive, standing recovery between tests. Prior to testing on the second day, players undertook a 20-min standardized warm-up consisting of 10 min of slow jogging, followed by 5 min of jogging and 5 min of sprints, accelerations, and jumps progressing in intensity. All tests were carried out in the afternoon between 16:00 h and 20:00 h on both testing days. Players were advised not to perform any physical exercise in the two days prior to the initial testing day and were given advice to ensure adequate hydration and nutritional status upon arrival for testing. One week after the second testing day, each player participated in a simulated basketball match on the same indoor basketball court with various external variables measured using LPS technology. Basketball players were previously familiarized with all physical fitness tests and the use of LPS devices during the 6-week pre-season phase (August-September). The testing sessions and simulated basketball matches took place during the in-season phase (November) across the 2019-2020 season.

130 **2.2. Participants**

131 Thirty youth, male basketball players aged between 13-18 years (age: 15.7 ± 1.7 years, height:
132 175.6 ± 11.6 cm, body mass: 61.5 ± 16.4 kg, body fat: $18.1 \pm 8.0\%$, training experience: $8.0 \pm$
133 4.1 years) volunteered to participate in this study. Players were classified according to their
134 chronological age as: U14 (n = 10, 14.0 ± 0.3 years, 163.8 ± 4.7 cm, 47.2 ± 4.9 kg, $19.8 \pm 4.5\%$,
135 6.0 ± 2.1 years), U16 (n = 10, 15.6 ± 0.6 years, 176.8 ± 4.6 cm , 59.0 ± 2.3 kg, $15.0 \pm 2.8\%$,
136 8.2 ± 2.7 years), and U18 (n = 10, 17.5 ± 0.7 years, 183.6 ± 6.0 cm , 78.4 ± 10.9 kg, $19.4 \pm$
137 11.4% , 10.1 ± 2.4 years). Statistical power calculations (G*Power, v3.1.9.2, Universität Kiel,
138 Germany) supported this sample size for comparisons between three groups using power =
139 0.80, $\alpha = 0.05$, and effect size = 0.60. Players belonged to the same elite basketball academy
140 (i.e., Spanish Asociación de Clubes de Baloncesto [ACB] League) being members of teams
141 competing at the highest competitive level in Spain for each age category. Players were
142 included in the study if they participated in the physical fitness testing sessions, participated in
143 official matches every week of the season, and did not sustain muscular or skeletal injuries in
144 the month prior to initial testing. Players and their legal guardians were informed of the
145 procedures, benefits, risks, and voluntary nature involved with participation in the study before
146 providing written informed assent (players) and consent (guardians). All procedures were
147 performed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki (2013) and were approved by the
148 Ethics Committee of the University Isabel I (Code: FUi1-PI002) before player recruitment
149 commenced.

150

151 **2.3. Physical fitness attributes**

152 *Linear sprinting test.* Players performed two maximal 20-m sprints [9], interspersed with a 90-
153 s passive, standing rest. Sprint times (s) at 5 m 10 m, and 20 m were taken as dependent
154 variables. Players were positioned 0.5 m behind the first photocell timing gate (Microgate™

155 Polifemo, Bolzano, Italy) to avoid inadvertent activation prior to commencing each sprint. All
156 photocell timing gates were positioned 0.4 m above ground level. Sprint time was automatically
157 activated as players triggered the first gate at the 0-m line. The fastest trial for each split time
158 was used for the subsequent analysis. The between-trial intraclass correlation coefficients
159 (ICCs) were 0.89, 0.95, and 0.97 for 5-m, 10-m, and 20-m sprint times, respectively.

160

161 *COD test.* The 505 COD test was used to assess COD speed in players. The 505 COD test
162 involved players sprinting forward 15 m from the starting point, pivoting 180° at a marked line,
163 and then sprinting for 5 m towards the start position [10] (Figure 1A). Players were free to
164 choose the preferred leg to plant and initiate the turn to perform the COD in each sprint. A
165 photocell timing gate (Microgate™ Polifemo, Bolzano, Italy) was positioned 0.4 m above
166 ground level and located 10 m from the start line to record the performance time (s) spanning
167 the 5 m directly before and 5 m directly after making the turn as the dependent variable. Players
168 completed two trials of the 505 COD test with 90 s of passive, standing rest applied between
169 trials. The fastest trial was used for subsequent analysis. The between-trial ICC for performance
170 time during the 505 COD test was 0.89.

171

172 *RCOD test.* A single trial of a RCOD test was administered consisting of five 30-m shuttle-
173 sprints (15 m forward, turn, 15 m forward in the opposite direction) interspersed with 30 s of
174 standing, passive rest between each shuttle [11]. Players commenced each shuttle 0.5 m before
175 the start line and sprinted forward for 15 m to touch a line on the floor with their preferred foot,
176 and then made a 180°-turn, before sprinting forwards to the starting line (Figure 1B). A single
177 photocell timing gate (Microgate™ Polifemo, Bolzano, Italy) was positioned 0.4 m above
178 ground level and placed at the start line to record performance time (s). The fastest single
179 shuttle time (RCODA_{best}) and the sum of all shuttle times (RCODA_{total}) were used for

180 subsequent analysis. The between-trial ICC for best and total time RCOD test has been reported
181 as 0.97 and 0.98, respectively [11].

182

183 ***** Figure 1A and 1B about here, please *****

184

185 *Jump testing.* Players completed two maximal bilateral countermovement jumps (CMJ) with
186 hands on hips separated by 30 s of passive, standing rest. Players were instructed to perform a
187 downward movement at a self-selected, comfortable depth followed by rapid extension of the
188 lower-limb joints during each jump. A photocell system (Optojump, Microgate™, Bolzano,
189 Italy) was used [12] to measure jump height (cm) calculated as: $h = gt/8$ (h, height, cm; g,
190 acceleration due to gravity, $9.81 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$; t, flight time of the jump, s) [13]. In addition, players
191 performed two maximal bilateral horizontal jumps (HJ) with arm swing permitted. Players
192 were instructed to place their toes on a marked line, then bend their knees to $\sim 120^\circ$ as quickly
193 as possible and rapidly jump as far forward as possible, remaining stationary after landing on
194 both feet. A metric tape was used to measure the jump distance (m) from the starting line to
195 the heel of the closest foot [14]. The highest CMJ and longest HJ were used for subsequent
196 analysis. The between-trial ICC for CMJ height was 0.99 and for HJ distance was 0.96.

197

198 **2.4. External demands during simulated matches**

199 The basketball simulated matches were played on a full court (28 x15 m) with five players per
200 team according to age category. Players performed three 4-min bouts interspersed with 2 min
201 of passive, standing rest between bouts [15]. Players within each age category were divided
202 into two balanced teams using evaluations of playing performance and positional role provided
203 by coaching staff [16]. Teams always remained the same during simulated matches. Official
204 basketball rules of the International Basketball Federation (FIBA) with standard competitive

205 rules were applied, with no technical or tactical restrictions and the clock paused during
206 stoppages [17]. The following regulations were also applied: 24-s shot clock; offensive and
207 defensive schemes selected by players; consistent verbal encouragement from coaching staff;
208 and the head coach of the team acted as the referee. The simulated matches were played on the
209 same court with a hardwood surface and started at 19:30 h for each age category. External
210 demands during simulated matches were measured using a portable LPS (WIMU PRO™;
211 Realtrack Systems SL, Almeria, Spain). Each player was fitted with a device (85 x 48 x 15
212 mm, 65 g) on the upper back using an adjustable harness, which was turned on 15 min before
213 the warm-up prior to simulated matches. Each device contains a receiver for the LPS connected
214 to six ultrawideband (UWB) antennae placed 4.5 m from the perimeter of the court at a height
215 of 3 m. The sampling frequency for positioning data was 20 Hz. An autocalibration of the
216 antennae was then carried out for 5 s. The device calculates the time required to receive the
217 signal and derives the unit position (coordinates X and Y) using one of the antennae as a
218 reference [18]. Data were analyzed using the system-specific software (S PRO WIMU
219 Software; Realtrack Systems SL, Almeria, Spain). The following external variables were
220 recorded from the LPS per min ($\text{m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) across the entire match to account for the varying
221 playing times across age categories given the variable nature of stoppages encountered: total
222 distance covered, distance covered cruising ($12.1\text{-}18.0\text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$), distance covered performing
223 high-speed running ($18.1\text{-}24.0\text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$), and distance covered sprinting ($> 24.1\text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$). These
224 speed zones are similar to those used in previous basketball studies [18–20]. Distance covered
225 while accelerating ($>0\text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$) and decelerating ($<0\text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$) were taken also recorded [21]. The
226 number of steps ($\text{n}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) and jumps ($\text{n}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) performed were also measured using 100-Hz
227 triaxial accelerometers, gyroscopes, and magnetometers within the devices. Acceptable intra-
228 unit (typical error of measurement = 1.2%) and inter-unit reliability (bias = 0.18) for total
229 distance covered across multidirectional paths has been reported for this LPS [22].

230

231 **2.5. Statistical analysis**

232 Data are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Normal distribution and homogeneity
233 of variance were assessed for all dependent variables using the Shapiro-Wilk and Levene tests.
234 Given sprint distance during matches was not normally distributed in U14 and U16 players,
235 sprint distance data were log transformed to allow for parametric analyses. The inter-player
236 coefficient of variation (CV) was used to assess the variability in physical fitness attributes and
237 external variables during simulated matches for each age category with the formula: $CV =$
238 $(SD/mean) \times 100$ [23]. One-way analyses of variance (ANOVA) with Bonferroni post hoc tests
239 were used to examine differences in physical fitness attributes and external demands during
240 simulated matches between age categories. Pairwise comparisons between age categories for
241 each outcome variable were expressed using the mean differences as: Mean difference ($\Delta\%$) =
242 $(\text{mean } 1 - \text{mean } 2) \times 100 / \text{mean } 2$. Cohen's effect sizes (ES) [24] were also calculated to
243 quantify the magnitude of difference for all pairwise comparisons using the following
244 thresholds for interpretation: *trivial*, ≤ 0.20 ; *small*, $0.20-0.59$; *moderate*, $0.60-1.19$; *large*, $1.20-$
245 1.99 ; *very large*, $2.00-3.99$; *extremely large*, ≥ 4.00 [25]. Pearson's product-moment correlation
246 coefficients (r) with 90% confidence intervals (CI) were used to quantify the relationships
247 between physical fitness attributes and external variables during simulated matches in each age
248 category. The magnitude of relationships was interpreted as follows: *trivial*, ≤ 0.10 ; *small*,
249 $0.11-0.30$; *moderate*, $0.31-0.50$; *large*, $0.51-0.70$; *very large*, $0.71-0.90$; and *nearly perfect*,
250 >0.90 [26]. When the 90% CI overlapped small positive and negative values, the magnitude
251 was deemed *unclear*. Linear regression analyses (R^2) were performed to identify the percentage
252 of variability in the external demands explained by each physical attribute. Data analyses were
253 carried out using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS 25.0, Chicago, IL, USA),
254 with statistical significance set at $p \leq 0.05$.

255

256 3. Results

257 Mean \pm SD and differences in physical fitness attributes according to age category are shown
258 in Table 1. Superior performance was observed in U16 and U18 players compared to U14
259 players in 20-m linear sprint ($p < 0.05$; *large-very large* effects), COD ($p < 0.05$; *large* effects),
260 RCOD ($p < 0.01$; *large-very large* effects), and HJ ($p < 0.01$; *large-very large* effects)
261 performance, and also in U18 players compared to U14 players in 10-m sprint ($p = 0.02$; *large*
262 effect) and vertical jumping ($p = 0.002$; *large* effect) performance.

263

264 *** Table 1 about here, please ***

265

266 Mean \pm SD and differences in external demands during simulated basketball matches according
267 to age category are shown in Table 2. U14 players covered less distance ($\text{m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) performing
268 high-speed running and sprinting compared to U16 ($p = <0.001-0.04$; *large* effect) and U18 (p
269 < 0.001 ; *very large* effect) players. In addition, U16 players covered more distance ($\text{m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$)
270 accelerating ($p = 0.05$; *large* effect) and decelerating ($p = 0.03$; *large* effect) compared to U18
271 players.

272

273 *** Table 2 about here, please ***

274

275 Table 3 shows the correlations while Table 4 shows the linear regression analyses between
276 physical fitness attributes and external demands during simulated basketball matches in each
277 age category. U14 players who were faster during linear sprints, the 505 COD test, and the
278 RCOD test (RCOD_{best} and RCOD_{total} times) covered greater total, cruising, and high-speed
279 running distances per minute during simulated matches (*large-very large*, $p < 0.05$; $R^2 = 0.33-$

280 0.66). In addition, U14 players who had faster 20-m sprint times (*very large*, $p = 0.031$; $R^2 =$
281 0.39) covered greater distances sprinting per minute during simulated matches. U14 players
282 who had faster $RCOD_{best}$ (*large*, $p = 0.02$; $R^2 = 0.47$) and $RCOD_{total}$ (*large*, $p = 0.03$; $R^2 = 0.43$)
283 times completed more jumps per minute during simulated matches.

284

285 U16 players who exhibited faster 5-m sprint times covered greater distances cruising per
286 minute during simulated matches (*very large*, $p = 0.004$; $R^2 = 0.66$) and those with faster 10-
287 m sprint times covered more distance accelerating per minute during simulated matches (*large*,
288 $p = 0.03$; $R^2 = 0.46$). U16 players demonstrating higher CMJ covered more distance sprinting
289 per minute during simulated matches (*nearly perfect*, $p = 0.013$; $R^2 = 0.91$) and those with
290 longer HJ covered more distance performing high-speed running (*very large*, $p = 0.05$; $R^2 =$
291 0.62) and sprinting (*nearly perfect*, $p = 0.024$; $R^2 = 0.89$) per minute during simulated matches.

292 U18 players who had faster 5-m sprint times covered greater high-speed running distances per
293 minute during simulated matches (*nearly perfect*, $p = 0.01$; $R^2 = 0.84$). Furthermore, U18
294 players with faster COD times (*nearly perfect*, $p = 0.008$; $R^2 = 0.86$) and higher CMJ (*very*
295 *large*, $p = 0.05$; $R^2 = 0.72$) covered more distance cruising per minute during simulated
296 matches.

297

298 *** Table 3 about here, please ***

299 *** Table 4 about here, please ***

300

301 4. Discussion

302 This study is the first to concurrently compare the physical fitness attributes and external
303 demands during match-play across different age categories in youth, male basketball players.
304 Furthermore, this study provides foundation data regarding the relationships between physical

305 fitness attributes and external match demands in youth, male basketball players from an elite,
306 Spanish basketball academy. The main results showed that while younger players (U14)
307 possessed inferior physical fitness across linear sprinting, COD, RCOD, and jumping tests
308 compared to older players (U16 and U18), they only demonstrated lower high-speed running
309 distance ($\text{m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) during simulated matches. In addition, U16 players covered more distance
310 ($\text{m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) accelerating and decelerating compared to U18 players during simulated matches
311 despite possessing similar physical fitness. Finally, players possessing superior physical fitness
312 tended to perform higher external demands during simulated matches, especially in the U14
313 age category.

314 Considering the importance of optimal physical conditioning for performance in youth
315 basketball [2], research has compared various physical fitness attributes across age categories
316 in youth players to aid in the development of targeted training strategies and to set age-
317 appropriate fitness goals [4,5]. The lower physical fitness evident in U14 players compared to
318 U16 and U18 players apparent in our study coincides with previous studies carried out in youth
319 Australian male and female basketball players aged 14-19 years [4,27]. Furthermore, we
320 observed non-significant, *small-moderate* differences in physical fitness attributes between
321 U16 and U18 players, suggesting that fitness may plateau when reaching the U16 age category
322 in youth, male basketball players. These results are in line with those reported for vertical jump
323 height, sprint speed, and aerobic capacity in young male and female Australian basketball
324 players aged 14-19 years [4], as well as jumping capacity, sprint speed, COD speed, and
325 repeated-sprint ability in elite, U16 and U18, Spanish, female players [6]. The lower physical
326 fitness in younger players, with increased homogeneity in physical fitness among older players
327 (U16 and U18 age categories) could be explained by the maturation process and the periodized
328 training strategies in each age category. Specifically, at ~13-14 years of age, disproportional
329 growth in leg length relative to trunk length may negatively affect coordination [28]. In turn,

330 impaired coordination could negatively impact player performance in fitness tests involving
331 movement patterns performed in an explosive manner and underpinned by precise
332 neuromuscular control such as sprinting, changing direction rapidly, and jumping. The
333 dissipation of these insufficiencies in motor coordination with maturation [29,30] as well as
334 the higher muscle mass and force production capabilities in older adolescents [31] may have
335 allowed the U16 and U18 players we examined to out-perform U14 players across the
336 basketball-specific fitness tests included. Furthermore, the absence of differences in physical
337 fitness between U16 and U18 players may be attributed to a plateau in peak muscle fiber size
338 evident during this stage of maturation [32]. Regarding training strategies, strength- and power-
339 focused training are not typically applied until later adolescence, which could also explain the
340 lower physical fitness in U14 players compared to older players given all tests involved rapid
341 expression of force. Consequently, it may be advisable to prescribe strength- and power-
342 oriented exercises as part of training plans in younger players to learn relevant exercise
343 techniques for an effective gradual progression of training across later stages of adolescence.
344 Given basketball high-performance and coaching staff aim to develop physical fitness
345 attributes in players to optimally prepare them for the demands faced during match-play,
346 comparisons in physical fitness between age categories in youth basketball players should be
347 accompanied by comparisons in match demands. Surprisingly, our data are the first on this
348 topic in basketball, showing U14 players covered less distance ($\text{m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) performing high-
349 speed running and sprinting during simulated matches compared to U16 and U18 players. It is
350 probable that U14 players are unable to achieve higher speeds ($>18.1 \text{ km}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) as readily during
351 isolated efforts and in a repeated manner as U16 and U18 players, which is reinforced by the
352 lower linear sprint speeds and RCOD performance observed in U14 players during the fitness
353 test battery. In this regard, future studies might consider speed capacities of youth basketball
354 players when delineating between movement intensities during matches by establishing speed

355 thresholds relative to the individualized maximum speed of each player [33]. Furthermore, U16
356 players covered greater distances ($\text{m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) accelerating and decelerating compared to U18
357 players during simulated matches, despite demonstrating non-significant differences in
358 physical fitness attributes emphasizing accelerative ability. These differences may be due to
359 the greater playing experience and subsequent superior sport competence in U18 players, which
360 likely leads to better interpretation of match scenarios and, subsequently, better positioning to
361 reduce rapid and explosive actions in response to unanticipated or unfamiliar match scenarios
362 [34].

363 Further to the comparisons in physical fitness and external demands during match-play
364 between age categories, our study is the first to examine the influence of physical fitness
365 attributes on external match demands using modern technologies (LPS devices) across different
366 age categories in youth basketball. Greater physical fitness led to higher external demands
367 performed during simulated basketball matches; however, the fitness attributes contributing
368 greatest to the variability in external demands during match-play were specific to each age
369 category. Specifically, linear sprint speed up to 20 m (40-51% shared variance with cruising,
370 high-speed running, sprinting, and total distance per minute), COD speed (36-46% shared
371 variance with cruising and total distance per minute), and RCOD speed (36-66% shared
372 variance with cruising distance, high-speed running distance, total distance, and jumps per
373 minute) were most strongly associated with external demands during simulated matches in U14
374 players, while linear sprint speed across 5 m (66-84% shared variance with cruising and high-
375 speed running distance per minute) and jumping capacity (62-89% shared variance with
376 cruising, high-speed running, and sprinting distance per minute) were most strongly associated
377 with external demands during simulated matches in U16 and U18 players. The higher
378 frequency of significant associations between fitness attributes and external demands during
379 simulated match-play in U14 players suggests physical capacities may exert a stronger impact

380 on match success in younger adolescent players given they possess inferior technical
381 proficiency compared to older adolescent players with longer histories of basketball training
382 exposure [35]. In support of this notion, training experience has been shown to be the primary
383 contributor to technical skill development in young basketball players [36]. On the other hand,
384 the significant associations between short sprint times (5-10 m) and cruising (U16),
385 acceleration (U16), and high-speed running (U18) distances per minute in older age categories
386 indicate accelerative capacity may become increasingly important to develop across the
387 maturation process in youth basketball players. Furthermore, the significant associations
388 between CMJ height and cruising distances (U18) as well as between HJ distance and high-
389 intensity running distance per minute (U16) during matches emphasize the importance of
390 developing of vertical and horizontal power expression in meeting external match demands in
391 older adolescent players. Indeed, vertical ($r = 0.45$) [37] and horizontal ($r = -0.67$) [38] jump
392 performance have been shown to underpin the ability to generate high speeds during linear and
393 multidirectional movement paths during isolated fitness tests in older adolescent (17.3 ± 0.5
394 years of age), representative, male basketball players; with our findings supporting these
395 relationships in match contexts. Collectively, these data show the importance of physical
396 fitness to execute match activities in youth basketball players, emphasizing specific attention
397 on developing accelerative ability and multi-directional lower-body power expression may be
398 needed to optimize physical capacities for on-court performance once players reach the U16
399 age category.

400 This study was subject to some notable limitations, which should be acknowledged. First, small
401 samples of players were recruited in each age category. Accordingly, further investigation is
402 encouraged in a larger sample of players using a wider range of age categories in youth players
403 (i.e., from U8 to U18) and expanding to adult players. Second, fitness attributes indicative of
404 aerobic capacity were not measured in this study. In turn, aerobic metabolic pathways are

405 heavily recruited during basketball match-play [20,39] and have been shown to influence high-
406 intensity activity distances during match-play in young, male basketball players [8]. Third,
407 internal variables such as heart rate and perceptual ratings were not measured during the
408 simulated matches, so future research could explore these variables to understand the
409 psychophysiological stress imposed on youth players according to age, as well as the influence
410 of physical fitness attributes on these responses. Fourth, maturity status was not able to be
411 measured in our study. Future research is encouraged to determine the maturity status of players
412 where permissible as a mechanism variable when exploring differences in physical attributes
413 and match demands across age categories in youth basketball players.

414

415 **5. Conclusions**

416 Physical fitness attributes and match activity vary across age categories in youth basketball
417 players. Specifically, our study showed younger players (U14) possessed inferior physical
418 fitness and executed less high-speed running distance ($\text{m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) during simulated matches
419 compared to older players (U16 and U18). Despite possessing similar physical fitness, U16
420 players covered more distance ($\text{m}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$) accelerating and decelerating during simulated
421 matches compared to U18 players. In turn, various physical fitness attributes were related to
422 external demands during simulated matches across all age categories, but most notably in U14
423 players. These data emphasize the importance of developing specific physical capacities to
424 accomplish the high rates of activity during match-play in youth, male basketball players.

425

426 **Declaration of interest**

427 None.

428

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442

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571

572 **Tables**573 **Table 1.** Differences in players' physical performance among age-category groups.

Physical fitness attributes	U14 (n = 10)		U16 (n = 10)		U18 (n = 10)		Pairwise comparisons (Δ %; p; ES)		
	Mean \pm SD	CV (%)	Mean \pm SD	CV (%)	Mean \pm SD	CV (%)	U14 vs. U16	U14 vs. U18	U16 vs. U18
<i>Linear sprint speed</i>									
5-m time (s)	1.08 \pm 0.05	4.26	1.06 \pm 0.09	4.28	1.02 \pm 0.04	8.39	1.68; 1.00 ; 0.26	5.24; 0.19; 1.20	3.50; 0.67; 0.54
10-m time (s)	1.90 \pm 0.08	4.56	1.83 \pm 0.10	4.13	1.78 \pm 0.08	5.23	3.76; 0.21; 0.79	6.29; 0.02 ; 1.41	2.44; 0.83; 0.49
20-m time (s)	3.39 \pm 0.17	4.19	3.17 \pm 0.15	5.04	3.08 \pm 0.13	4.80	7.02; 0.007 ; 1.38	10.11; <0.001 ; 2.08	2.89; 0.66; 0.63
<i>Change-of-direction (COD) speed</i>									
505 COD time (s)	2.56 \pm 0.18	5.13	2.34 \pm 0.11	6.97	2.37 \pm 0.12	4.50	9.25; 0.004 ; 1.53	8.11; 0.02 ; 1.28	1.04; 1.00; 0.22
<i>Repeated COD speed</i>									
RCODA _{best} (s)	7.80 \pm 0.38	4.00	7.23 \pm 0.29	4.92	7.02 \pm 0.28	3.95	7.92; 0.001 ; 1.71	11.22; <0.001 ; 2.37	3.06; 0.49; 0.76
RCODA _{total} (s)	47.78 \pm 2.45	4.95	44.11 \pm 1.59	5.13	43.34 \pm 2.14	3.61	8.32; 0.001 ; 1.81	10.24; <0.001 ; 1.93	1.77; 1.00; 0.41
<i>Jump height and distance</i>									
CMJ height (cm)	28.31 \pm 3.88	16.64	33.16 \pm 6.73	13.70	37.62 \pm 6.26	20.31	-14.63; 0.34; -0.91	-24.75; 0.002 ; -1.84	11.85; 0.44; 0.69
HJ distance (m)	1.81 \pm 0.20	6.88	2.12 \pm 0.21	10.93	2.22 \pm 0.15	10.13	-14.67; 0.01 ; -1.51	-18.84; <0.001 ; -2.39	4.88; 0.85; 0.59

Note: Bolded p values indicate significant pairwise difference ($p \leq 0.05$). SD: standard deviation; CV: inter-player coefficient of variation; U14: under 14 years age category; U16: under 16 years age category; U18: under 18 years age category; Δ %: difference in means as percentage between age categories; ES: effect size; CMJ: countermovement jump; HJ: horizontal jump.

574

575

576 **Table 2.** Differences in the external responses encountered by basketballers during simulated matches among age-category groups.

External variables	U14 (n = 10)		U16 (n = 10)		U18 (n = 10)		Pairwise comparisons (Δ %; p; ES)		
	Mean \pm SD	CV (%)	Mean \pm SD	CV (%)	Mean \pm SD	CV (%)	U14 vs. U16	U14 vs. U18	U16 vs. U18
<i>Distance variables (m·min⁻¹)</i>									
Total distance	93.99 \pm 9.26	4.34	97.69 \pm 6.60	9.85	96.48 \pm 4.19	6.75	-3.79; 0.79; -0.47	-2.59; 1.00; -0.37	1.25; 1.00; 0.22
Cruising (12.1-18.0 km·h ⁻¹)	18.90 \pm 6.34	7.73	23.53 \pm 2.81	33.54	23.71 \pm 1.83	11.93	-19.68; 0.08; -1.01	-20.28; 0.14; -1.18	-0.74; 1.00; -0.08
High speed running (18.1-24.0 km·h ⁻¹)	1.04 \pm 0.83	37.23	2.18 \pm 1.01	79.87	3.31 \pm 1.23	46.48	-52.11; 0.04 ; -1.23	-68.56; <0.001 ; -2.20	-34.36; 0.11; -1.01
Sprinting (> 24.0 km·h ⁻¹)	0.10 \pm 0.32	103.74	0.69 \pm 0.72	319.33	0.82 \pm 0.85	105.01	-85.31; 0.02 ; -1.12	-87.73; 0.02 ; -1.23	-16.51; 1.00; -0.17
Accelerating	17.28 \pm 0.90	4.40	17.84 \pm 0.56	5.21	16.84 \pm 0.74	3.15	-3.11; 0.30; -0.76	2.62; 0.77; 0.54	5.91; 0.05 ; 1.53
Decelerating	17.20 \pm 0.83	3.98	17.79 \pm 0.62	4.83	16.73 \pm 0.67	3.50	-3.34; 0.21; -0.82	2.80; 0.63; 0.63	6.35; 0.03 ; 1.65
<i>Frequency variables (n·min⁻¹)</i>									
Steps	100.81 \pm 14.27	11.49	101.36 \pm 11.07	14.15	90.64 \pm 10.41	10.92	-0.54; 1.00; -0.04	11.22; 0.25; 0.82	11.82; 0.23; 1.00
Jumps	1.07 \pm 0.64	40.49	1.29 \pm 0.73	59.28	0.94 \pm 0.38	56.05	-17.10; 1.00; -0.33	14.12; 1.00; 0.26	37.66; 0.71; 0.64

Note: Bolded p values indicate significant pairwise difference ($p \leq 0.05$). SD: standard deviation; CV: coefficient of variation among players; U14: under 14 years age category; U16: under 16 years age category; U18: under 18 years age category; Δ %: difference in means as percentage between age categories; ES: effect size.

578 **Table 3.** Relationships (r) with a 90% confidence interval (CI) between players' physical performance and physical external responses during
 579 basketball simulated matches in each age-category group.

Age category	Physical fitness attributes	Distance variables (m·min ⁻¹)						Frequency variables (n·min ⁻¹)	
		Total distance	Cruising	High-speed running	Sprinting	Accelerating	Decelerating	Steps	Jumps
U14	5-m sprint time (s)	-0.69; ±0.34* L	-0.68; ±0.35* L	-0.60; ±0.40* L	-0.45; ±0.47 M	0.08; ±0.55 ?	-0.02; ±0.55 ?	-0.44; ±0.47 M	-0.44; ±0.47 M
	10-m sprint time (s)	-0.69; ±0.34* L	-0.72; ±0.32* VL	-0.62; ±0.39* L	-0.57; ±0.41 L	-0.14; ±0.54 ?	-0.23; ±0.53 ?	-0.59; ±0.40* L	-0.59; ±0.40 L
	20-m sprint time (s)	-0.63; ±0.38* L	-0.65; ±0.37* L	-0.66; ±0.36* L	-0.62; ±0.39* L	-0.10; ±0.55 ?	-0.18; ±0.54 ?	-0.56; ±0.42 L	-0.60; ±0.40 L
	505 COD time (s)	-0.68; ±0.35* L	-0.60; ±0.40* L	-0.48; ±0.46 M	0.36; ±0.50 M	-0.28; ±0.52 ?	-0.35; ±0.50 M	-0.55; ±0.42 L	-0.28; ±0.52 ?
	RCOD _{best} (s)	-0.60; ±0.40* L	-0.70; ±0.33* VL	-0.82; ±0.23** VL	0.38; ±0.50 M	0.06; ±0.55 ?	-0.02; ±0.55 ?	-0.44; ±0.47 M	-0.69; ±0.34* L
	RCOD _{total} (s)	-0.68; ±0.35* L	-0.73; ±0.31* VL	-0.79; ±0.26** VL	0.45; ±0.47 M	0.00; ±0.55 ?	-0.08; ±0.55 ?	-0.54; ±0.43 L	-0.66; ±0.36* L
	CMJ height (cm)	0.62; ±0.39 L	0.43; ±0.48 M	0.18; ±0.54 ?	-0.11; ±0.55 ?	0.41; ±0.48 M	0.47; ±0.46 M	0.52; ±0.44 L	0.26; ±0.53 ?
	HJ distance (m)	0.15; ±0.54 ?	0.26; ±0.53 ?	0.59; ±0.40 L	-0.22; ±0.53 ?	0.08; ±0.55 ?	0.07; ±0.55 ?	-0.19; ±0.54 ?	0.58; ±0.41 L
U16	5-m sprint time (s)	-0.57; ±0.41 L	-0.81; ±0.24** VL	-0.58; ±0.41 L	-0.32; ±0.51 M	0.57; ±0.41 L	0.57; ±0.41 L	-0.54; ±0.43 L	-0.25; ±0.53 ?
	10-m sprint time (s)	-0.36; ±0.50 M	-0.59; ±0.40 L	-0.58; ±0.41 L	-0.06; ±0.55 ?	0.68*; ±0.35* L	0.62; ±0.39 L	-0.24; ±0.53 ?	-0.21; ±0.54 ?
	20-m sprint time (s)	-0.35; ±0.50 M	-0.56; ±0.42 L	-0.58; ±0.41 L	-0.34; ±0.51 m	0.57; ±0.41 L	0.49; ±0.45 M	-0.29; ±0.52 ?	-0.22; ±0.53 ?
	505 COD time (s)	0.27; ±0.52 ?	0.12; ±0.55 ?	-0.13; ±0.55 ?	-0.41; ±0.48 M	-0.20; ±0.54 ?	-0.33; ±0.51 M	0.14; ±0.54 ?	-0.21; ±0.54 ?
	RCOD _{best} (s)	-0.01; ±0.55 ?	-0.31; ±0.51 ?	-0.50; ±0.45 M	-0.28; ±0.52 ?	0.37; ±0.50 M	0.30; ±0.52 ?	-0.05; ±0.55 ?	-0.09; ±0.55 ?
	RCOD _{total} (s)	-0.03; ±0.55 ?	-0.32; ±0.51 M	-0.48; ±0.46 M	-0.34; ±0.51 M	0.35; ±0.50 M	0.27; ±0.52 ?	-0.09; ±0.55 ?	-0.16; ±0.54 ?
	CMJ height (cm)	0.50; ±0.45 M	0.59; ±0.40 L	0.65; ±0.37 L	0.96; ±0.06 NP*	-0.49; ±0.45 M	-0.21; ±0.54 ?	0.59; ±0.40 L	0.18; ±0.54 ?
	HJ distance (m)	0.60; ±0.40 L	0.63; ±0.38 L	0.79; ±0.26* VL	0.93; ±0.10* NP	-0.31; ±0.51 ?	0.02; ±0.55 ?	0.63; ±0.38 L	0.32; ±0.51 M
U18	5-m sprint time (s)	0.53; ±0.43 L	-0.09; ±0.55 ?	0.92; ±0.11** NP	0.66; ±0.36 L	-0.59; ±0.40 L	-0.65; ±0.37 L	0.34; ±0.51 M	0.18; ±0.54 ?
	10-m sprint time (s)	0.54; ±0.43 L	-0.09; ±0.55 ?	0.54; ±0.43 L	0.10; ±0.55 ?	-0.11; ±0.55 ?	-0.22; ±0.53 ?	0.20; ±0.54 ?	-0.02; ±0.55 ?
	20-m sprint time (s)	0.51; ±0.45 M	-0.08; ±0.55 ?	0.60; ±0.40 L	0.14; ±0.54?	-0.26; ±0.53 ?	-0.36; ±0.50 M	0.26; ±0.53 ?	-0.03; ±0.55 ?
	505 COD time (s)	-0.06; ±0.55 ?	-0.93; ±0.10** NP	0.16; ±0.54 ?	0.47; ±0.46 M	-0.17; ±0.54 ?	-0.08; ±0.55 ?	0.05; ±0.55 ?	0.05; ±0.55 ?
	RCOD _{best} (s)	0.49; ±0.45 M	-0.55; ±0.42 L	0.49; ±0.45 M	0.26; ±0.53 ?	-0.22; ±0.53 ?	-0.19; ±0.54?	0.11; ±0.55 ?	-0.01; ±0.55 ?
	RCOD _{total} (s)	0.24; ±0.53 ?	-0.52; ±0.44 L	0.23; ±0.53 ?	-0.02; ±0.55 ?	-0.19; ±0.54 ?	-0.16; ±0.54?	0.09; ±0.55 ?	-0.19; ±0.54 ?
	CMJ height (cm)	-0.06; ±0.55 ?	0.85; ±0.20* VL	-0.25; ±0.53 ?	0.62; ±0.39 L	0.32; ±0.51 M	0.23; ±0.53 ?	0.11; ±0.55 ?	0.04; ±0.55 ?
	HJ distance (m)	0.17; ±0.54 ?	0.18; ±0.54 ?	0.06; ±0.55 ?	0.43; ±0.48 M	0.33; ±0.51 M	0.25; ±0.53 ?	0.14; ±0.54 ?	0.52; ±0.44 L

Note: U14: under 14 years age category; U16; under 16 years age category; U18: under 18 years age category; COD: change-of-direction; RCOD_{best}: best time during the repeated-change-of-direction test; RCOD_{total}: total time during the repeated-change-of-direction test; CMJ: countermovement jump; HJ: horizontal jump. * p <0.05; ** p <0.01. Correlation magnitudes: ?, unclear (90%CI overlapped small positive and negative values); S, small (r = ≤0.20); M: moderate (r = 0.21-0.50); L, large (r = 0.51-0.70); VL, very large (r = 0.71-0.90); NP, nearly perfect (r = >0.90).

Table 4. Linear regression (R^2) analyses between physical fitness attributes and external variables during simulated basketball matches according to age category in youth basketball players.

Age category	Physical fitness attributes	Distance variables ($\text{m} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$)						Frequency variables ($\text{n} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$)	
		Total distance	Cruising	High-speed running	Sprinting	Accelerating	Decelerating	Steps	Jumps
U14	5-m sprint time (s)	0.472*	0.459*	0.362*	0.123	0.006	0.000	0.194	0.194
	10-m sprint time (s)	0.470*	0.512**	0.379*	0.322	0.019	0.053	0.343	0.351
	20-m sprint time (s)	0.399*	0.424*	0.438*	0.388*	0.010	0.031	0.310	0.359
	505 COD time (s)	0.457*	0.355*	0.330	0.128	0.079	0.125	0.299	0.076
	RCOD _{best} (s)	0.362*	0.488*	0.664**	0.153	0.030	0.000	0.197	0.473*
	RCOD _{total} (s)	0.462*	0.532**	0.627**	0.199	0.000	0.007	0.292	0.433*
	CMJ height (cm)	0.378	0.181	0.032	0.011	0.169	0.222	0.265	0.067
	HJ distance (m)	0.023	0.068	0.348	0.048	0.006	0.006	0.035	0.333
U16	5-m sprint time (s)	0.328	0.661*	0.332	0.103	0.321	0.324	0.291	0.062
	10-m sprint time (s)	0.127	0.350	0.335	0.04	0.463*	0.382	0.056	0.045
	20-m sprint time (s)	0.126	0.313	0.332	0.114	0.322	0.241	0.085	0.047
	505 COD time (s)	0.072	0.014	0.016	0.168	0.042	0.110	0.019	0.046
	RCOD _{best} (s)	0.000	0.093	0.248	0.077	0.135	0.088	0.002	0.007
	RCOD _{total} (s)	0.001	0.103	0.234	0.112	0.119	0.072	0.008	0.024
	CMJ height (cm)	0.254	0.346	0.417	0.905*	0.236	0.046	0.353	0.031
	HJ distance (m)	0.361	0.395	0.621*	0.858*	0.095	0.000	0.398	0.105
U18	5-m sprint time (s)	0.287	0.008	0.842**	0.429	0.342	0.416	0.115	0.032
	10-m sprint time (s)	0.284	0.009	0.287	0.010	0.012	0.049	0.039	0.000
	20-m sprint time (s)	0.257	0.006	0.363	0.019	0.069	0.129	0.067	0.001
	505 COD time (s)	0.003	0.858**	0.027	0.223	0.030	0.006	0.003	0.002
	RCOD _{best} (s)	0.236	0.299	0.238	0.069	0.046	0.037	0.013	0.000
	RCOD _{total} (s)	0.058	0.266	0.053	0.000	0.036	0.027	0.007	0.036
	CMJ height (cm)	0.003	0.722*	0.063	0.383	0.101	0.055	0.013	0.002
	HJ distance (m)	0.028	0.033	0.003	0.183	0.106	0.063	0.019	0.274

Note: U14: under 14 years age category; U16; under 16 years age category; U18: under 18 years age category; COD: change-of-direction; RCOD_{best}: best time during the repeated-change-of-direction test; RCOD_{total}: total time during the repeated-change-of-direction test; CMJ: countermovement jump; HJ: horizontal jump. * $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$.

580 **Figures legends**

581 **Figure 1.** Description of the change of direction ability (505-CODA) (1A) and repeated
582 change of direction ability (RCODA) (1B) tests.

1A)

583

1B)

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